

Correlation between “very early” age fracture performance and evolution of rheological properties of high performance fiber reinforced cementitious composites with adapted rheology

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Abstract

The tremendous advances in concrete technologies our society is witness of, do not only provide the construction industry with new advanced materials and processing/manufacturing techniques, but also require the performance of cement based materials to be investigated not only in its structural service state, but also throughout its *very early* and *early* age life.

Tailored successful placement and development of mechanical performance, even in the first hours of life, can affect the structural durability and discriminate about the successful accomplishment of the structural performance throughout the service life. In this paper reference is made to a High-Performance Fibre-Reinforced Cementitious Composite, formulated with adapted rheology to ease its placement and most of all to achieve a tailored alignment of the fibres through the casting flow.

The development of tensile and shear fracture properties in the first hours (up to three) after the first contact between cement and water has been studied with an ad-hoc designed test set-up. The knowledge of such properties is of the utmost importance to foster the use of these kind of advanced cement based materials with adapted rheology in precast construction, where the design of transient situations, including demoulding and handling, may play a crucial role, also in the sight of optimizing the productivity.

In a quality control framework, the development of tensile and shear fracture properties of the investigated materials in the considered time frame have been also correlated to the evolution of rheological properties, so far evaluated through a mini-slump flow tests.

Keywords: Concrete; rheology; tensile strength; shear strength; *very early* age properties; *3D printing*.

1. Introduction

Concrete and, more generally, cementitious materials are the most used materials in construction owing to many advantageous inherent features, such as relatively low cost, high durability, good fire performance, “tailorability” and on-site free shaping.

Despite concrete is considered as a traditional material, it has experienced an intensive process of continuous improvement in the last decades, leading to the formulation of very advanced material, as examples High- and Ultra-High Performance Concretes (HPC), Self-Compacting Concretes (SCC) and Ultra-High Durable Concretes (UHDC, [1-2]).

In the very last years, a further drive to concrete development has been represented by *concrete 3D printing*, which aims at combining the free on-site shaping typical of cementitious materials with the digital fabrication, in order to reduce construction time and cost, while increasing the overall quality and work safety [3].

All these improvements have their roots in the enhancement of concrete rheology brought in by SCC and UHPC technologies, which allow very low water-to-cement ratios and, consequently, very dense and resistant materials. Adapted concrete rheology also fosters the introduction of different types of fibers, even in relevant amount (up to 3 % by volume), thus providing extraordinary toughness and ductility to concrete. The formulation of strain-hardening concrete in tension is nowadays something quite easy to be reached.

In most cases, rheology is the key *very early* age property (namely, in the first few hours after casting), since it has to be tailored in order to guarantee concrete pouring and air expulsion without vibration, while avoiding fibers and aggregates segregation. Furthermore, shrinkage should be limited, so to reduce possible micro-cracking during hardening, this being detrimental for stiffness and durability. *Concrete 3D printing*, however, gives a major role also to *very early* age tensile, shear and compressive strengths, since they govern, together with rheology of course, the overall manufacturing process. In *concrete 3D printing*, this has a direct impact on deposition layout and velocity, and vertical inclination.

Starting from the study by Mettler et al. (2016) [4], an experimental approach is described in this paper for the assessment of the very early age fracture behaviour of concrete, focusing on the time evolution of tensile and shear strengths, in the very first hours after casting. The final aim is to apply such approach for the study of *3D-printable* concretes.

2. Very early age properties

2.1. Rheology

As well known, fresh concrete can be addressed as a yield stress fluid, characterized by a minimum value of stress to be applied in order to active irreversible deformation and to trigger flow [5]. In particular, concrete behaves as a Bingham fluid, *i.e.*, once the yield limit τ_{lim} is attained, tangential stress τ is linearly proportional to the shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$ through the plastic viscosity μ_p (namely, $\dot{\gamma} = 0$ for $\tau < \tau_{lim}$ and $\tau = \tau_{lim} + \mu_p \cdot \dot{\gamma}$ for $\tau \geq \tau_{lim}$ [6-9]).

The rheological parameters (yield stress and plastic viscosity) can be evaluated by means of different types of rheometers (depending on aggregate sizes) or via far simpler (but less exhaustive) procedures such as slump test [9]. The determination of the rheological properties of concrete, however, is made rather tricky by the thixotropic behavior, inducing a variation of fresh properties with time, and by the shear rate effect [10-14].

Rheological properties are very important for practical applications [15-16], as an example in the case of self-compacting and fiber-reinforced concretes, and especially in rather new technologies, first of all *concrete 3D printing*. In the case at hand, a preliminary investigation has been conducted based on slump test, which provides an indirect indication about the yield stress.

2.2. Tensile and shear strengths

Tensile strength is generally considered as secondary property in concrete, since the mechanical performance of reinforced concrete structures usually relies on the tensile behavior of reinforcing bars. On the other hand, the increasing attention to fiber-reinforced concrete, durability and advanced manufacturing processes, makes fracture behavior of concrete a key parameter. Shear behavior should be also properly addressed, since, even though mainly linked to tensile strength, it can be influenced by aggregate interlock and by the formation of compressed struts confined by fibers (if any). In the particular case of *concrete 3D printing*, shear behavior is instrumental in directly addressing the problem of layer-to-layer bond, in which the orientation of fiber is the main influencing parameter.

3. Test setup and materials

3.1. Testing devices

In order to investigate the evolution of tensile and shear strengths with time, in the very first hours after casting, two special test setups have been manufactured according to the schemes reported in Figure 1 (plan view and picture of the actual systems, [17]).

The molds are made of transparent polycarbonate so to check during loading if significant stratification takes place through the specimen thickness.

Figure 1. Setups for tension (left) and shear (right) tests. (dimensions in cm).

The tensile test device consists of two separate rectangular molds (grey and white in Figure 1a, top). The opening between the two parts is narrowed at mid-length by two semi-circular elements so to locally reduce the cross-section and consequently localize the fracture. As shown in Figure 1a (bottom), small pins have been introduced in the lateral faces of each of the two molds, in order to limit as possible concrete-to-mold slippage.

Similarly, the shear test device consists of two separate rectangular molds (grey and white in Figure 1b, top). In this case no pins have been introduced, since slippage should not occur, being the fracture plane parallel to the direction of motion.

Both tests were displacement-controlled thanks to a small electromechanical actuator, and load has been measured via a 600 N-capacity load-cell. The displacement velocity adopted was equal to 0.05 mm/s and 0.10 mm/s for tensile and shear tests, respectively.

It is worth noting that friction during the motion of the movable molds (grey part in Figure 1a-b, top) is non-negligible with respect to the strength of fresh concrete. Hence, friction coefficient has been evaluated experimentally, by applying two separate weighs on the two molds of each device and performing the test. The thus estimated friction contribution has been then deducted from the force-displacement curves.

In this preliminary investigation aimed at assessing the effectiveness of the experimental procedure, slump has been assessed via a small cone (top diameter = 70 mm, bottom diameter = 100 mm, height = 65 mm) before each strength test, so to have an indirect indication about yield stress evolution.

3.2. Materials

The mixes planned for the experimental investigations are reported in Table 1. In particular, Mix M120 with 120 kg/m³ of steel fiber has been recently studied, while the other 3 concretes, with decreasing amounts of fiber, will be tested in the next months, in order to deepen the effect of fiber content on the variation with time of *very early* age properties.

Concrete has been cast by firstly mixing for 1 min cement and slag (slowly pouring water in the latter 30 s) and then adding the superplasticizer. Afterwards, sand and fibers have been introduced, both of them after 2 min of mixing. Finally, concrete has been mixed for 3 min. Then concrete has been quickly poured in the mold, in order to force the material to pass through the future fracture plane so fostering fibers alignment.

Table 1. Concrete mixes.

	M120	M80	M40	M00
CEM II 42.5 [kg/m ³]	600	600	600	600
Slag [kg/m ³]	500	500	500	500
Water [kg/m ³]	200	200	200	200
Superplasticizer [l/m ³]	33	33	33	33
sand 0-2 mm [kg/m ³]	982	982	982	982
steel fiber [kg/m ³]	120	80	40	0

4. Test Results

4.1. Slump test

Slump tests have been performed in the range of 0 min - 200 min after casting, and the spread diameter in two orthogonal directions has been measured. A schematic representation of slump test spread is provided in Figure 2a, while its average depth is reported in Figure 2b for different time durations after casting. From Figure 2b it is clear that (1) already at 3 h after casting slump spread is negligible and (2) the experimental dots lie in a curve with upward concavity. From preliminary experimental results on the other 3 mixes, it seems that the evidence (1) depends mainly on cement mortar (no significant difference being observed among the concretes), while the outcome (2) depends on fiber content, since downward concavity has been observed for far lower fiber content.

Figure 2. Slump test: a) schematic representation of slump spread and b) average spread as a function of time after casting.

4.2. Tensile strength

Tensile tests have been performed in the range 40 min -200 min after casting, since for smaller time durations concrete was too fluid for providing any tensile resistance.

In Figure 3a the typical failure of the specimen is represented. Thanks to the reduced resistant area, failure always occurred at the mid-span section. The analysis of the fracture surface showed that a very good alignment of the fibers along the axis of the specimens and just a slight downward segregation of the same fibers.

A critical point, however, is represented by the non-homogeneous hydration of the specimen, usually faster at the exposed top surface.

In Figure 3b, the nominal stress – displacement curves are reported, while in Figure 4a and b, tensile strength and fracture energy are shown as functions of time duration after casting. Fracture energy has been computed as integral of the whole nominal stress – displacement curve. As expected, both properties increase with time, tensile strength with an exponential law, while fracture energy with a logarithmic trend.

Figure 3. Tensile test: a) specimen at failure and b) nominal stress – displacement curves for different time durations after casting.

Figure 4. Tensile test: a) strength and b) fracture energy at different time durations.

4.3. Shear strength

Shear tests have been performed approximatively in the range 40 min - 200 min after casting. In Figure 5a one of the typical failure mode of the specimen is represented.

Figure 5. Shear test: a) specimen at failure and b) nominal stress – displacement curves for different time durations after casting.

Figure 6. Plot of a) nominal stress – displacement curves in shear test for different time durations after casting, and b) tensile and shear strength against slump spread loss (η_{slump}).

Failure modes in shear appear to be slightly more complex than in tension, due to a tension-compression induced by the formation of inclined concrete struts in some cases. The analysis of the fracture surface showed a very good alignment of the fibers across the fracture, and a non-homogeneous hydration of the specimen has been observed as well. In Figure 5b, the nominal stress – displacement curves are shown for different times after casting, while in Figure 6a shear strength evolution with time is reported. Shear strength appeared to increase with an exponential law as for tensile strength, even though more rapidly in both absolute and normalized terms. In Figure 6b, tensile and shear strength are plotted as functions of the slump spreading loss, expressed as:

$$\eta_{slump} = (d_{spreading}^t - d_{cone}) / (d_{spreading}^{t_0} - d_{cone})$$

where $t_0 = 0$ min.

5. Concluding remarks and outlooks

A testing procedure has been developed to assess the *very early* age properties of concrete, by evaluating slump flow, tensile and shear strengths. The tailored test setups consist of polycarbonate molds in which concrete is poured just after mixing and then directly tested at a given time duration after casting. Mechanical characterization is accompanied by mini slump tests, whose results are linked to concrete yield stress.

Tensile and shear strength tests in the range 40 min - 200 min after casting have been performed, showing an exponential increase with time, sharper in the case of shear behavior. Fracture energy showed a logarithmic increase with the time.

Further investigations on mixes with different amounts of fiber together with rheometer tests will allow (1) to better highlight the direct role of fiber in the evolution of the mechanical behavior and (2) to correlate the development of rheological and mechanical properties. Finally, a setup for compression test is under evaluation, this being instrumental for the detection of the failure envelope of concrete. This information could allow to monitor the evolution of the fracture process in concrete.

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